

Online Shopping Trends among College Students in Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar City

Dr. Rajendra Nanasaheb Shelar

Assistant Professor

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar College of Arts & Commerce, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar

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Abstract: E-commerce platforms are growing in the techno-based era. India's techno-savvy youths impacting the market are widely used e-commerce platforms. The present research paper studies the online shopping trends among college students in Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar city of Maharashtra state. The volume of online transactions by college students is increasing. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar is a growing city. It was necessary to study the growing online shopping trend among the college students. This research paper study an online buying behaviour, motivating and influencing factors, payment method, risk and problems faced and satisfaction level of students about e-shopping. The convenience sampling method (As per willingness of students) used to select samples. Student voluntarily participated in e-survey through questionnaire link of google form. The primary data collected and presented through a tables and figures has been analysed.

Keywords: E-commerce, Online Shopping, Trend, College students, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of e-commerce platforms is increasing in the fast-paced life. The current era is based on technology. Today's young generation is techno-savvy and influenced by the internet. India has a large youth population is impacting the market are widely used e-commerce platforms. The network of online shopping companies widely across different cities the county. The present research paper studies the online shopping trends among college students in Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar city of Maharashtra state. This city has a large scale youth population studying in the colleges.

Significance of the research paper:

Times are changing; the volume of online transactions is increasing, so the use of e-commerce platforms for online shopping is rising. College students use smartphones regularly and are therefore constantly active on the internet and social media. It was necessary to study the growing online shopping trend among the college students. Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar is a growing city. As per 2011 census, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar city population was more than 11 lakhs. The estimated population in 2026 is approximately 18 lakhs. A large number of students are pursuing higher education among different colleges in this city.

Objectives of the research paper:

1. To study an online shopping behaviour of college students
2. To analyse the motivating and influencing factors on e-shopping
3. To know the payment mode used by students
4. To study the risk and problems faced by students while e-shopping
5. To know the overall satisfaction level of students who preferred e-shopping

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Source of data:

Primary data: The present research paper is wholly based on online field survey. To collect data, researcher conducted an online field survey through questionnaire made with google form. Data has been collected from college students in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar city.

The questions regarding e-shopping trend among college student were categorised based on the following points:

- **Buying behaviour:** the questions used to study e-buying behaviour are relate to
 - ✓ Frequency of purchase products (e-buying frequency)
 - ✓ Mostly preferred shopping platforms (choice of e-shopping websites)
 - ✓ Mostly preferred commodity (choice of product)

- **Buying motives:**

Motivating factors for e-shopping

- **Influencing factor:**

Factors influencing product preference

- **Mode of payment:**

Mostly preferred payment method

Mostly preferred payment app

- **Risk and problems faced by respondents:**

Risk factors feel by respondents while shopping online

Problem faced while shopping online

- **Satisfaction level of respondents:**

Satisfaction level of respondents while e-shopping

Rating based on online shopping experience

Sampling procedures:

Sampling method: samples were being selected as per convenience sampling method. (As per willingness of students) Student voluntarily participated in e-survey through questionnaire link plotted with google form on their whatsApp groups

Sample size: Total 80 students were voluntarily participated in online survey from 11 colleges in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar city. The link to the questionnaire created through google form was sent to whatsApp groups of students in different colleges.

Area of study: Graduation & post-graduation students among colleges in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar city.

Scope of the research paper:

Geographical scope: Voluntarily participation of college students in online survey of colleges in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar city

Age wise & course wise scope: Participation of graduation & post-graduation students aged approximately between 18 to 24 years

Limitations of the research paper:

This research paper relies on voluntarily responses from college students.

Geographical limit: This research paper for students of colleges in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar city only

Numbers/samples limit: Total 80 students were voluntarily participated in online survey from 11 colleges

Time limit: Survey period during October 2025 to January 2026

3. ANALYSIS OF DATA

The primary data collected has been analysed by tabulation, classification through the following means:

- ✓ Tables
- ✓ Figures
- ✓ Interpretations

The data presented through a total of 4 tables and 8 figures has been analysed. Only selected tables and figures have been mentioned for the research paper.

Table 1: Classification of Respondents

Gender wise:	Number	%
Male	49	61.25
Female	31	38.75
Total	80	100
Course wise:		
Graduation	52	65
Post-graduation	28	35
Total	80	100

Table 1 indicates gender wise and course wise classification of respondents (students) participated in online survey through google form questionnaire. Total 80 students respond to concern survey, out of them 49 Male (61.25%) and 31 (38.75%) were the female participants. 65 percent students belong to graduation and 35 percent from post-graduation, respond to concern online survey.

Figure 1

Figure 1 shows the frequency of online shopping by college students in Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar city. Mostly students (45 percent) buy seasonally, 41.25 percent monthly, 11.25 percent weekly and remaining only 2.5 percent students buy frequently.

Table 2: Mostly preferred e-shopping platforms

Shopping platforms	Responses	%	Rank
Flipkart	56	33.94	1
Amazon	46	27.88	2
Meesho	36	21.82	3
Shopsy	10	6.061	4
Mynta	8	4.848	5
Nykaa	3	1.818	7
Other	6	3.636	6
Total Responses	165	100	

Table 2 shows the e-commerce website used preferentially by respondents. Respondent have selected more than one e-shopping platform respectively. Hence, e-shopping platforms ranked according to respondents preferences. Total of 165 responses (mostly favoured preference) have been received for the above questions.

Majority of the students (33.94 percent) preferred Flipkart website (rank 1) for e-buying, 27.88 percent used Amazon, 21.82 percent Meesho, remaining used another platforms such as Shopsy (6.06%), Myntra (4.84%), Nykaa (1.81%) and Other (3.63%) like Snapdeal, Ajoio, DeoDap, big basket, Robu.in, H&M & Zara also.

Table 3. Mostly Preferred product by respondents

Products	Responses	%	Rank
Cloths/Apparel	49	26.63	1
Electronic items	37	20.11	2
Educational materials	26	14.13	3
Footwear	25	13.59	4
Beauty/Cosmetics	24	13.04	5
Healthcare and fitness products	14	7.609	6
Consumer goods (FMCG)	7	3.804	7
Other	2	1.087	8
Total Responses	184	100	

Table 3 indicates the mostly preferred items while online shopping by the respondent. Respondent have selected more than one product respectively. Hence, products ranked according to respondents preferences. Total 284 responses have been received for the concern question. 26.63 percent students responded that they buy cloths/apparel (rank 1) through e-shopping platforms. 20.11 percent preferred for electronic items, 14.13 percent for educational items, 13.59 percent for footwear, 13.04 percent for beauty/cosmetic products, 7.6 percent for healthcare items, 3.8 percent respondent prefer consumer goods (FMCG) and remaining are preferred for other items like wrist-watch or needed items.

Table 4. Motives behind online shopping

Motive factors	Responses	%	Rank
Saves time	51	30.91	1
Discount & Offers	46	27.88	2
Doorstep Delivery	34	20.61	3
Variety of products	34	20.61	3
Total responses	165	100	

Table 4 shows the factors that motivate online shopping. Respondents respond to more than one motive factor, therefore total 165 responses received, Motive factors were ranked in order of priority given by respondents.

Saves time is the top purchase motivator, receiving the highest 30.91% of responses, followed by 27.88 percent (rank2nd) for discount and offers, 20.61 percent (rank3rd) for both doorstep delivery and for variety of products available on online store simultaneously.

Figure 2

Figure 2 indicates the factors that affect online shopping when choosing a product. Majority (41.25 percent) of the respondents make online purchases based on online reviews. Followed by social media (21.25%), cheap prices (18.75%), friends recommendation (12.5%), Advertisement (5%) and other (1.25%) reasons.

Figure 3

Figure 3: Majority (48.75%) of respondent used cash on delivery method to make a payment for online purchases. Followed by 43.75 percent respondents used payment apps, remaining 7.5 percent used debit card, no one used credit card to payment.

Figure 4

Figure 4 indicates that for which payments app mostly respondents give their highest priority. It is clearly seen that PhonePe app used by highest (51.25%) of respondents, Gpay used by 25percent respondents, paytm by 12.5 percent, BHIM app by 6.25 percent and five percent respondent used other apps for online payment.

Figure 5

Figure 5 shows that what factors feels risky to respondents while online shopping; 42.5 percent respondents feel that there is a lack of choice to touch and feel a product before purchase. 27.5 percent are feel risk of identity theft, 15 percent feel that breach of payment details, 13.75 percent respondents never trust on online shopping, 1.25 percent respondent experienced fake product.

Figure 6

Figure 6 clearly reveals that the 55 percent respondent fully satisfied regards online shopping. 38.75 percent are partly satisfied and remaining 6.25 percent respondents are not satisfied regards online shopping.

Figure 7

Figure 7 shows that problems faced by respondents while online shopping. 47.5percent respondents faced quality issues of purchased product. 20percent experienced fault in product, 12.5percent faced delivery issue, 10percent faced safety about product and remaining 10 percent respondent had not face any problem while shopping online.

Figure 8

Figure 8 show, Respondents rating online shopping based on their experience while e-buying. Majority 41.25% respondent gave Good rating, 13.75% respondents experienced Excellent, 37.5% gave Average rating and remaining 7.5 percent gave Poor rating for online shopping experience.

Findings of the research paper:

Major findings are summarized as follows:

Buying behaviour:

E-buying Frequency: Mostly 45 percent of respondents shop online seasonally, followed by 41.25 percent respondents shop online at least every month.

Preferable e-shopping platforms: Flipkart website is ranked number one in terms of online shopping. Majority 33.94 percent respondents shop online from the Flipkart website (rank1st); also 27.88 percent (rank2nd) respondents use the Amazon for e-shopping and 21.82 percent (rank3rd) use Meesho.

Most preferred commodity: while shopping online, 26.63 percent of respondents give the highest priority (rank1st) to clothing, followed by 20.11 percent of students who gave the second priority to electronic items, followed by 14.13 percent (rank3rd) for educational items, 13.59 percent (rank4th) for footwear and 13.04 percent (rank5th) for beauty/cosmetic products.

Buying motives:

Motivating factors for e-shopping: Saves time is the top (rank1st) purchase motivator, receiving the highest 30.91 percent of responses, followed by (27.88 %) rank 2nd for discount and offers, 20.61 percent (rank3rd) for both doorstep delivery and for variety of products available on online store simultaneously.

Influencing factor:

Factors influencing product preference: Majority 41.25 percent of the respondents make online purchases based on online reviews. Followed by social media (21.25%), cheap prices (18.75%) and friends recommendation (12.5%).

Mode of payment:

Mostly preferred payment method: Majority (48.75%) of respondent used cash on delivery method for payment of online purchases. Followed by 43.75 percent respondents used payment apps and 7.5 percent use debit card.

Mostly preferred payment app: Mostly respondents give their highest priority to PhonePe app. Majority (51.25%) of respondents use PhonePe to make payment. 25% respondents use google pay also paytm use by 12.5 percent respondents.

Risk and problems faced by respondents:

Risk factors feel by respondents when shopping online: Mostly students (42.5%) feel it risky that they are not being able to touch the products before e-shopping, 27.5% students are afraid of their identity being stolen. Also, 15% are afraid of their payment details being compromised.

Problem faced while shopping online: 47.5 percent respondents face quality issues in online shopping. 20% respondent experienced receiving faulty good also 12.5 percent encountered delivery issue while shopping online.

Satisfaction level of respondents:

Satisfaction level of respondents while e-shopping: The highest numbers of respondents, 55% percent, are fully satisfied regards online shopping. 38.75 percent are partly satisfied and only the remaining 6.25 percent of respondents are not satisfied with online shopping.

Rating based on e-shopping: Ratings given by respondents based on their online shopping experience. The majority 41.25% respondent gave Good rating, 13.75% of respondents had an excellent experience and 37.5% gave Average rating for online shopping experience.

4. CONCLUSION

- ✓ Mostly college students e-shop seasonally, followed by some who buy at least monthly
- ✓ According to student's responses, Flipkart is the most preferred website, followed by amazon in second place.
- ✓ Students give the highest preference to buying clothes online, followed by electronic items and then educational materials.
- ✓ The biggest motivating factor for online shopping is time saving, followed by discount & offers, then home delivery & availability of variety of products simultaneously.

- ✓ Mostly online reviews influenced students e-shopping, followed by social media and then cheap price of products respectively.
- ✓ Most of the students (48.75%) pay in cash, and some (43.75%) pay through payment apps. Only few (7.5%) students use debit card to pay.
- ✓ PhonePe is the most favourable payment app among the college students then google pay and paytm respectively.
- ✓ Major risk factors feel by the students that they are not being able to touch the products before e-shopping, they afraid of their identity being stolen and they also feel that their payment details being compromised.
- ✓ Students faced quality issues, receiving faulty good also encountered delivery issue while shopping online.
- ✓ More than half (55%) of the students are fully satisfied about online shopping some of the students (38.75%) are partly satisfied.
- ✓ Majority of the students (40%) had a good experienced with online shopping, about 13% of students had an excellent experience, and 37% had an average experience.

REFERENCES

- [1] Online field survey through structured questionnaire in google form.